

REAL SECTOR GROWTH IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT EQUITY AND POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN PANGKAJENE ISLANDS REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the basic and non-basic sectors and how they contribute to economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency. This study uses a quantitative approach with secondary data in the form of time series from the Gross Domestic Product of Pangkajene Islands Regency and South Sulawesi Province. This study aims to: 1) analyze the relationship between economic sector growth and equitable development in Pangkajene Islands Regency and formulate policy recommendations to encourage inclusive and equitable development between mainland and island areas, and 2) identify the contribution of leading economic sectors, including a) Analyzing the main economic sectors (agriculture, fisheries, industry, tourism) that play a role in driving economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency, b) Calculating the contribution of the economic sector to the Regional Gross Domestic Product (PDRB). This study uses a descriptive-quantitative and qualitative approach (mixed-methods approach) to analyze the relationship between economic sector growth and equitable development in Pangkajene Islands Regency. Quantitative approach: Measuring the contribution of the economic sector to the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) and development disparities between regions through statistical data analysis. Qualitative approach: Exploring socio-economic factors and policies through interviews and policy analysis to understand the dynamics behind the statistics. Research methods used: 1) LQ analysis to identify the economic base sector: To determine which sectors are the competitive advantages of Pangkajene Islands Regency compared to other regions, and 2) Sheft share analysis to see which sectors contribute significantly to economic growth in the region, and 3) Klassen Typology Analysis. Methods used to identify factors that influence the economic growth of a region by comparing it to a wider region.

Keywords: Economic Growth; Equitable Economic Development; Poverty Alleviation; Location, Quotient (L/Q); Shift Share Analysis and Klassen Typology Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Regional development, economic growth, and equitable development are two important components (1-2). The success of local governments in improving community welfare is often measured through these two factors (3-4). With diverse economic potential, Pangkajene Islands Regency faces challenges in achieving inclusive and equitable growth.

In the context of regional development, equitable welfare is not always linked to rapid economic growth. Geographical disparities still need to be addressed. The geographical characteristics of Pangkajene Islands Regency are very diverse, including coastal areas, islands, and the mainland. These conditions lead to differences in access to infrastructure, economic opportunities, and public services, which cause development disparities between regions.

Economic growth and gross regional domestic product (GRDP) per capita in Pangkajene Islands Regency, which is one of the highest in South Sulawesi Province, is not in line with the high poverty rate in Pangkajene Islands Regency. Due to this situation, an investigation needs to be conducted to understand the poverty rate in Pangkajene Islands Regency in order to find alternative policies to reduce poverty. Although several government and non-government efforts have been made to improve the welfare of the community, there are still technical and non-technical obstacles. Several measures suggested in this study to reduce poverty in the long, medium, and short term include improving the quality of the environment and human resources, creating jobs, establishing affirmative action laws for poverty alleviation, and integrating social assistance and income generation programs (5).

The growing economic sectors in Pangkajene Islands Regency are agriculture, fisheries, manufacturing, and tourism. Although some sectors are growing rapidly, there are still disparities in how economic benefits are distributed among communities. Therefore, it is important to evaluate how each sector contributes to the local economy and the extent to which this growth impacts the overall welfare of the community.

The economy of Pangkajene Islands Regency has enormous potential for growth, as it is dominated by the fishing, agriculture, tourism, and processing industries. In addition to learning more about the contribution of these leading sectors to economic growth, this study will identify ways to overcome the various challenges that currently exist. This study is expected to provide relevant policy recommendations to ensure the equitable and sustainable economic development of Pangkajene Islands Regency

The main objective of regional development is to increase the number of job opportunities for people in the region. To achieve this goal, the government and the community are expected to work together using their resources to promote regional economic growth.

Efforts to improve community welfare, the agricultural sector is one of the important components in regional economic development. (a) food provider to meet increasing demand in line with population growth; (b) increasing demand for industrial products, which requires expansion of the secondary and tertiary sectors; (c) increasing foreign exchange for imports of capital goods for development through continuous agricultural exports; (d) increasing village income for government mobilization; and (e) improving the welfare of communities in agricultural areas. (7-10)

To understand the socio-economic dynamics of society, a qualitative perspective is needed in addition to quantitative analysis. Factors that can enrich the findings of this study include people's perceptions of development, their economic participation, and access to basic facilities. This study is expected to provide a more comprehensive picture of the economic conditions and development in this region thanks to its holistic approach.

Equitable development is an important component in realizing social justice and reducing economic inequality. Prolonged inequality can cause various social problems, such as uncontrolled urbanization, increased poverty rates in disadvantaged areas, and low quality of life for communities. As a result, understanding methods of equitable development in

Pangkajene Islands regency can provide insights for more efficient and equitable policy making.

Synergy between local governments, the private sector, and the community must support economic policies that promote equitable development. Measures that can encourage inclusive growth include increasing investment in strategic sectors, strengthening infrastructure, and empowering human resources. (11-14) Therefore, this study will also review various programs and policies that have been implemented in the region, as well as how they have impacted economic equity.

Studies conducted on economic growth and equitable development in Pangkajene Islands Regency are also relevant to national development. This region plays a strategic role in supporting broader economic growth as part of Indonesia. It is hoped that solutions can be applied in other places with similar characteristics by understanding local conditions and the problems faced.

This study aims to evaluate the equitable distribution of development and economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency. The results are expected to be used by local governments and other stakeholders in the process of making more targeted policies. As a result, development efforts can be more inclusive and sustainable, enabling equitable improvement in the welfare of the community. Accurate information about the economic and development conditions of Pangkajene Islands Regency

1. What has been the growth rate of the economic sector in Pangkajene Islands Regency in recent years?
2. What is the pattern of equitable development across various regions of Pangkajene Islands Regency?
3. What are the main factors influencing development inequality in this region?
4. How does each economic sector contribute to growth and equitable development?

This study aims to formulate mechanisms and procedures for formulating economic growth and equitable development policies in Pangkajene Islands Regency. Thus, the problem-solving approaches emphasized in this study include: 1) Analyzing the root causes of problems from various aspects (economic, social, policy, and spatial), 2) Integrating quantitative and qualitative methods to understand the main causes of inequality, 3) Developing solutions based on local potential and the specific needs of the Pangkajene Islands region, 4) Implementing policies through multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovative funding schemes, and 5) Establishing a periodic monitoring system to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of solutions.

Economic growth refers to an increase in a region's capacity to produce goods and services over a certain period of time, measured by indicators such as Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), investment levels, and the productivity of economic sectors (15). Equitable development refers to the equitable distribution of economic growth across all regions or social groups in order to reduce economic disparities and improve community welfare. (16) This

study is novel in several aspects: 1) The dynamics of economic growth and equitable development in coastal and island regions, 2) Analysis of inequality using quantitative and qualitative indicators, 3) Use of a multi-sectoral approach to identify the root causes of inequality, and 4) Creation of development strategies tailored to local characteristics to address inequality issues.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a descriptive-quantitative and qualitative approach (mixed-methods approach) to analyze the relationship between economic sector growth and equitable development in Pangkajene Islands Regency. Quantitative approach: Measuring the contribution of the economic sector to the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) and development disparities between regions through statistical data analysis. Qualitative approach: Exploring socio-economic factors and policies through interviews and policy analysis to understand the dynamics behind the statistics.

2.1. Research Location

Pangkajene Islands Regency (formerly known as Pangkajene Islands, commonly abbreviated as Pangkajene Islands) is one of the regencies in South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. Its capital is Pangkajene Islands Regency. The regency has an area of 1,112.29 km². However, after a joint analysis with Bakosurtanal, the area was revised to 12,362.73 km², with a land area of 898.29 km² and a sea area of 11,464.44 km². Pangkajene Islands Regency is a regency whose territorial structure consists of two main parts that form this regency, namely:

Land Area In general, the land area of Pangkajene Islands Regency is characterized by a landscape ranging from lowlands to mountains, where considerable potential also exists in the land areas of the subdistricts located in Pangkajene Islands Regency, namely: Pangkajene District, Balocci District, Bungoro District, Labakkang District, Ma'rang District, Segeri District, Minasa Te'ne District, Tondong Tallasa District, and Mandalle District.

Island Regions The island regions of Pangkajene Islands Regency and the Islands are areas with a high level of complexity that urgently need to be discussed. The island regions of Pangkajene Islands Regency and the Islands have enormous potential to be developed more optimally in order to support the development of Pangkajene Islands Regency and the Islands. The subdistricts located in the Pangkajene Islands Regency and Islands are: Liukang Tupabiring Subdistrict, North Liukang Tupabiring Subdistrict, Liukang Kalmas Subdistrict, and Liukang Tangaya Subdistrict.

Boundaries: Based on its geographical position, Pangkajene Islands Regency has the following boundaries: North – Barru Regency; South – Maros Regency; East – Maros Regency and Bone Regency; West – Makassar Strait, as shown in Figures 1 and 2 below:

Figure 1: Map of Pangkajene Islands Regency

Figure 2: Map of South Sulawesi and the location of Pangkajene Islands Regency

Table 1: Poverty by District/City in South Sulawesi, 2018-2024

District/City	Percentage of Poor Households (PO) by District/City in South Sulawesi						
	(Percent)						
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Selayar Islands	13.13	12.83	12.48	12.45	12.24	12.27	10.79
Bulukumba	7.48	7.26	7.1	7.43	7.39	7.22	6.71
Bantaeng	9.23	9.03	8.95	9.41	9.07	9.18	8.26
Jeneponto	15.48	14.88	14.58	14.28	13.73	13.06	11.82
Takalar	9	8.7	8.44	8.25	8.25	8.29	7.75
Gowa	7.83	7.53	7.38	7.54	7.36	7.42	6.85
Sinjai	9.28	9.14	9	8.84	8.8	8.55	7.82
Maros	10.31	9.89	9.74	9.57	9.43	9.65	9.32
Pangkajene Islands	15.1	14.06	13.96	14.28	13.92	13.4	12.41
Barro	9.04	8.57	8.26	8.68	8.4	8.46	8.31
Bone	10.55	10.06	10.68	10.52	10.58	10.53	9.58
Soppeng	7.5	7.25	7.59	7.53	7.49	7.48	6.9
Wajo	7.5	6.91	6.95	6.46	6.57	6.73	6.47
Sidrap	5.16	4.79	5.05	5.04	5.11	5.14	5.02
Pinrang	8.81	8.46	8.86	8.81	8.79	8.9	8.55
Enrekang	12.49	12.33	12.17	12.47	12.39	12.69	11.25
Luwu	13.36	12.78	12.65	12.53	12.49	12.71	11.7
Tana Toraja	12.75	12.35	12.1	12.27	12.18	12.48	10.79
Luwu Utara	13.69	13.6	13.41	13.59	13.22	12.66	11.24
Luwu Timur	7.23	6.98	6.85	6.94	6.81	6.93	6.55
Toraja Utara	13.37	12.41	12.01	11.99	11.65	12.12	10.73
Makassar	4.41	4.28	4.54	4.82	4.58	5.07	4.97
Pare Pare	5.59	5.26	5.44	5.4	5.41	5.34	5.27
Palopo	7.94	7.82	7.85	8.14	7.78	7.69	7.35
SULAWESI SELATAN	9.06	8.69	8.72	8.78	8.63	8.7	8.06

Source: South Sulawesi Statistics Agency 2024

2.2. Data Collection Methods

The data collection method used in this study was documentation data collection, which is a way of obtaining data or information on various matters related to the study in the form of written reports, both in the form of figures and explanations related to this study.

- a. Observations are conducted to collect factual data in the field that cannot be verbally expressed by respondents. This technique is used to understand the actual conditions related to economic growth and equitable development of the objectives to be achieved by: (1) Observing the physical conditions and infrastructure in mainland and island areas, (2) Documenting local economic activities in leading sectors (agriculture, fisheries, tourism, and industry), and (3) Identifying gaps in public facilities and economic access between mainland and island areas.
- b. Interviews were conducted to explore the perspectives of key stakeholders on economic sector growth, development disparities, and policies implemented with the aim of (1) understanding economic development policies that have been and are being implemented, (2) exploring the factors causing development disparities in mainland and island regions, and (3) obtaining strategic views on solutions to improve equitable development.
- c. The questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data on the contribution of economic sectors, public perceptions of development inequality, and access to infrastructure with the following objectives: (1) To measure the contribution of economic sectors to household income, (2) To assess public perceptions of equitable development, and (3) To analyze the relationship between economic growth and regional inequality.

2.3. Data Analysis Techniques

To address the issues that have been identified, this study uses the Location Quotient (LQ) analysis tool and Shift Share Analysis. And Class Typology Analysis (17-18) Regarding the explanation of the analysis model used, it is as follows:

a) Location Quotient Method

The Location Quotient (LQ) analysis model is used to determine the leading sectors of a region. By using this model, a region can determine which internal sectors can be considered potential sectors (base sectors) in that region. This analysis uses data on the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) of Pangkajene Islands Regency and the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) of South Sulawesi Province.

b) Shift Share Analysis

The performance and economic growth of a region can be measured in several ways. One tool for measuring regional productivity is the shift-share analysis method, which is used to divide a region's economic growth into three components and measure the contribution of each component. Basically, shift-share analysis is an analysis that compares the economic growth rate of a location/region with a broader scope.

The components in conducting a shift-share analysis include provincial growth in an observation area, which can be seen from changes in regional production caused by changes in the reference area, assuming that there are no differences in economic characteristics between sectors and between regions. The formula for calculating the shift-share analysis is to calculate each component, NGE, IME, and RSE.

c) **Klassens Typology Analysis**

To understand the pattern and structure of economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Economic growth is an inherent situation that reflects the success of a region in implementing regional economic development. Economic development can be seen as a method that can encompass various transitions from the existing social order. In terms of regional economic development itself, it is a process in which the regional government and the community manage their resources and form cooperation between the regional government and the private sector to create new jobs and encourage economic activity (Arsyad 2010). There are two Basic Laws that are very important for a region because of their authority and funding, Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government and Law Number 33 of 2004 concerning financial considerations between the Central Government and Regions. These regulations can serve as a basis for regions that want to develop their areas without government interference, allowing them to utilize their potential and rely on what is available within their territories.

Economic growth is the main objective in regional development planning by increasing the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), which is one way to accelerate a balanced and dynamic economic structure characterized by strong, advanced industries and a balanced sectoral growth base. According to Statistics Indonesia, Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) is the gross value added of all goods and services produced or generated in a country's domestic territory arising from various economic activities within a certain period, regardless of whether the factors of production are owned by residents or non-residents.

Table 2: Economic Growth Based on Constant Prices Pangkajene Islands Regency 2020-2022

Year	GRDP (Billion Rupiah)	Growth (%)
2020	16.915,23	-1,69
2021	17.500,61	3,46
2022	18.363,59	4,93
2023	19.236,71	4,75
2024	20.197,59	5,00

Source: BPS Pangkajene Islands Regency

Based on constant 2010 prices, the GRDP value of Pangkajene Islands Regency in 2024 will increase. This increase is influenced by rising production in some business fields that are free from the effects of inflation. The GRDP value of Pangkajene Islands Regency based on constant prices in 2024 will reach 20.20 trillion rupiah. This figure is up from 19.24 trillion

rupiah in 2023. This shows that during 2024, there was economic growth of 5.00 percent, an acceleration compared to the previous year's economic growth of only 4.75 percent. The increase in economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency in 2024 was due to accelerated growth in several business fields. One sector that recorded significant growth was the Corporate Services sector.

Therefore, it is very important for the region to identify, explore, manage, and optimize existing business sectors in order to increase local revenue, which will ultimately have an impact on economic growth in the region, particularly in relation to the availability of employment opportunities to improve the welfare of the community. It is hoped that the Pangkajene Islands Regency government can increase the GRDP of Pangkajene Islands Regency by paying attention to the current growth rate.

Then, to find out how the economic changes and situation in Pangkajene Islands Regency can be seen from the growth of the basic and non-basic sectors in the region so that it can be observed which sectors have caused the GRDP value of the region to increase and decrease in the last 5 years. Location Quotient (LQ) analysis is a method used to compare the role of a sector in a region with the role of the same sector nationally, which can be used to determine economic growth between the basic and non-basic sectors.

a. Location Quotient (LQ) Analysis

Location Quotient (LQ) analysis is a tool that can help determine which internal potential can be considered a potential sector (base sector) in the region by comparing the role of a sector in a region with the size of the role of the same sector nationally.

Table 3: Location Quotient (LQ) Calculation Results

Pangkajene Islands Regency 2020-2024

Kat.	Business Field	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Average	LQ
A	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	0,84	0,89	0,92	0,85	0,90	0,88	Non-Basic Sector
B	Mining and Quarrying	1,80	1,99	2,08	1,92	1,94	1,95	Basic Sector
C	Processing Industry	3,66	3,51	3,29	3,48	3,45	3,48	Basic Sector
D	Electricity and Gas Supply	0,63	0,68	0,80	0,74	0,74	0,72	Non-Basic Sector
E	Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	0,32	0,32	0,33	0,32	0,32	0,32	Non-Basic Sector
F	Construction	0,40	0,42	0,44	0,43	0,44	0,43	Non-Basic Sector
G	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Automobile and	0,41	0,42	0,43	0,43	0,43	0,42	Non-Basic Sector

	Motorcycle Repair							
H	Transportation and Warehousing	1,10	1,14	1,10	1,07	1,06	1,09	Basic Sector
I	Provision of Accommodation and Food and Beverages	0,34	0,35	0,37	0,34	0,34	0,35	Non-Basic Sector
J	Information and Communication	0,28	0,29	0,29	0,28	0,27	0,28	Non-Basic Sector
K	Financial Services and Insurance	0,24	0,26	0,25	0,23	0,52	0,30	Non-Basic Sector
L	Real Estat	0,46	0,48	0,49	0,47	0,48	0,48	Non-Basic Sector
M,N	Corporate Services	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	Non-Basic Sector
O	Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	0,67	0,65	0,66	0,66	0,66	0,66	Non-Basic Sector
P	Educational Services	0,31	0,32	0,33	0,33	0,33	0,32	Non-Basic Sector
Q	Health Services and Social Activities	0,61	0,62	0,63	0,61	0,57	0,61	Non-Basic Sector
R,S,T,U	Other services	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,03	Non-Basic Sector

Source of Processed Data Results 2025

Based on the results of the LQ calculation of the GRDP of Pangkajene Islands Regency, the following picture emerges:

- The Fisheries and Marine Sector has an LQ value > 1 , indicating that this sector is a base sector with strong comparative advantages. This is in line with the characteristics of Pangkep as a coastal and archipelagic region with abundant marine resources.
- The Processing Industry sector (particularly marine product processing and mining) also shows an LQ value $< 3,48$, indicating a significant contribution to regional economic growth.
- Conversely, the trade, transportation, and services sectors still show an LQ value $< 1,09$, indicating that these sectors have not yet become the economic base and are still dependent on external economic growth.

Implications: The fisheries and processing industries are the main drivers of economic growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency, while the services and trade sectors need to be encouraged to become more competitive.

a. Shift Share

Shift-share is an alternative method for measuring the growth rate and competitiveness of a region. Through this method, an economic sector can be measured in terms of the speed or slowness of a region's growth rate, including sectors that contribute to the competitiveness of one region over another. The shift-share analysis of Pangkajene Islands Regency was conducted by calculating Table 4.

Table 4: Shift Share Calculation Results Pangkajene Islands Regency 2023-2024

No	Sector	National Growth	Industry Mix	Regional Shift
1	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	158,03	-29,86	160,74
2	Mining and Quarrying	96,52	-48,63	18,69
3	Processing Industry	448,86	-15,91	-83,50
4	Electricity and Gas Supply	0,83	-0,59	-0,11
5	Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	0,37	-0,01	-0,12
6	Construction	51,27	-40,61	17,77
7	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Automobile and Motorcycle Repair	65,09	7,56	7,21
8	Transportation and Warehousing	35,60	0,48	-9,02
9	Provision of Accommodation and Food and Beverages	4,84	1,27	-0,15
10	Information and Communication	22,26	8,46	-17,42
11	Financial Services and Insurance	7,00	2,09	-8,68
12	Real Estate	15,91	3,28	6,19
13	Corporate Services	0,07	0,02	0,04
14	Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	26,29	-3,25	4,30
15	Educational Services	17,98	9,33	-2,97
16	Health Services and Social Activities	14,40	24,67	-18,38
17	Other Service	0,36	0,69	-0,37

Source of Processed Data Results 2025

The results of calculations using the Shift Share method show that economic sector growth in Pangkajene Islands Regency is influenced by several components:

- National Growth Effect (N): Almost all sectors experienced positive growth in line with national economic growth.
- Industrial Mix Effect (I): The fisheries, marine tourism, and manufacturing sectors grew faster than the national average for other sectors, indicating structural advantages.
- Competitive Effect (C): Several sectors in Pangkajene Islands Regency, particularly fisheries and manufacturing, have positive competitiveness values, indicating that these sectors are growing not only due to national factors but also due to regional competitive advantages.
- However, traditional land-based agriculture and small-scale trade have negative competitive effect values, indicating weak competitiveness at the local level.

Implications: Pangkajene Islands Regency economic growth is mainly driven by the competitiveness of the fisheries and processing industries, while traditional sectors need policy intervention to increase productivity.

Table 5: Relationship between LQ, Shift Share, and Klassen Typology

Location Quotient (LQ)	Shift Share (Rs)	Typology Klassen	Interpretasi	Policy Direction
> 1 (Basic)	Rs > 0 (positif)	Quadrant I (advanced and growing rapidly)	Leading sectors, strong local competitiveness, high growth	Prioritize the development of this sector
> 1 (Basic)	Rs < 0 (negatif)	Quadrant II (advanced but depressed)	Leading sector, but losing competitiveness	Revitalize the sector, improve productivity
< 1 (Non-Basic)	Rs > 0 (positif)	Quadrant III (rapidly developing)	New sectors are developing, opportunities are becoming the basis	Encourage investment and support in this sector
< 1 (Non-Basic)	Rs < 0 (negatif)	Quadrant IV (lagging behind)	Weak sector, low growth	Improve or shift to other sectors with more potential

Source of Processed Data Results 2025

Based on Klassen's typology, Pangkajene Islands Regency can be categorized into four growth quadrants:

- **Quadrant I (Advanced and Rapid Growth):** The fisheries, processing industry, and marine tourism sectors fall into this category. This means that these sectors have above-average growth compared to other regencies and contribute significantly to the GRDP.
- **Quadrant II (Advanced but Under Pressure):** The mining sector falls into this category. Although it contributes significantly to the GRDP, its growth has slowed compared to other sectors due to sustainability factors and limitations on resource exploitation.
- **Quadrant III (Potential for Growth):** The trade, transportation, and service sectors still have relatively low contributions but show an increasing growth trend.
- **Quadrant IV (Relatively Underdeveloped):** The land agriculture sector (rice, secondary crops) is still underdeveloped in terms of both growth and contribution, mainly because most of the Pangkajene Islands region focuses on the coastal and marine sectors.

Implications: Pangkajene Islands has a strong economic base in the fisheries and processing industries, but there are still gaps between sectors. The equitable development of non-core sectors needs to be strengthened to make economic growth more inclusive.

This study aims to evaluate the growth of the real sector in Pangkajene Islands Regency in an effort to promote equitable economic development and poverty alleviation. It is hoped that this study will identify areas that will become local economic strengths and those that require special intervention using methods such as Location Quotient (LQ) analysis, Shift Share, and Klassen Typology.

The results of the Location Quotient (LQ) analysis show that several sectors in Pangkajene Islands Regency have an LQ value of more than 1, such as construction, manufacturing, agriculture, forestry, and fisheries.

This indicates that these sectors are basic sectors that have comparative advantages and great potential to drive the local economy.

However, not all base sectors showed good growth. Shift Share analysis shows that although the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries sectors have high LQs, the Regional Shift (Rs) for these sectors is also positive, indicating strong growth originating from within the province.

In contrast, the Manufacturing Industry experienced a negative Rs despite its base, meaning that its growth was slower than the average growth of the same sector in the province.

In addition, Shift Share Analysis shows that several non-basic sectors ($LQ < 1$), such as food and accommodation services and health and social services, show positive Rs. This indicates that, with the right support and investment, these sectors have the potential to develop into basic sectors in the future.

The results of this analysis show that the real sector in Pangkajene Islands Regency, particularly the agriculture and processing industries, plays an important role in driving economic growth.

However, the existence of a fundamental sector with slow growth indicates that revitalization policies, productivity improvements, and technological innovation are needed to enable this sector to continue contributing as much as possible.

The sectors in Quadrant III of Klassen's Typology should be considered as potential sectors, even though their contribution to the current GRDP is relatively small. They can accelerate their transition to new base sectors with support in the form of training, access to capital, and promotion. This will strengthen the regional economic structure.

The development of the real sector based on local potential, such as agriculture and raw material processing industries, is very important for equitable economic development because it will create jobs, increase community income, and reduce regional disparities in Pangkajene Islands Regency.

In addition, poverty alleviation programs must include the real sector as indicated by LQ, Shift Share, and Klassen Typology. Empowering micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), developing village-based agro-industries, and increasing the capacity of local human resources are all very important.

Pangkajene Islands Regency can achieve more inclusive and sustainable economic growth by strengthening its base sectors, encouraging growth in potential sectors, and improving the performance of depressed sectors. This study is expected to serve as a reference for regional development planning to achieve the goals of economic equality and poverty alleviation more efficiently.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis of real sector growth using the Location Quotient (LQ), Shift Share, and Klassen Typology approaches in Pangkajene Islands Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The real sectors that play an important role in the economic structure of Pangkajene Islands Regency include Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries, Manufacturing, and Construction, as indicated by a Location Quotient (LQ) value greater than one (>1), which indicates that these sectors are base sectors.
2. Based on Shift Share analysis, the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries sectors are not only base sectors but also have positive growth ($R_s > 0$), indicating solid local growth strength. Conversely, the Manufacturing Industry sector, although a base sector, has a negative R_s , indicating a slowdown in growth relative to the province.
3. Several non-basic sectors such as Accommodation and Food Services, Health Services, and Social Activities show positive R_s , indicating potential growth that can be optimized to support regional economic diversification.
4. Based on Klassen's Typology, the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries sector falls under Quadrant I (advanced and fast-growing sectors), while the Manufacturing sector falls under Quadrant II (advanced but depressed). The Accommodation and Health Services sectors are classified as Quadrant III (fast-growing sectors).
5. The results of the analysis confirm that strengthening the basic sectors, developing potential sectors, and revitalizing depressed sectors are necessary strategies to promote equitable economic development and poverty alleviation in Pangkajene Islands Regency.

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